

IPBES - invasive alien species assessment: Chapter 6.

Data management report of Table of knowledge and data gaps

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Description

The table synthesizes the most important knowledge and data gaps identified and collated through the assessment. Confidence levels in the summary for policymakers were allocated with full consideration of these gaps, which, if closed, would strengthen the understanding of biological invasions. Experts have assessed the estimated costs, scientific challenge to close these gaps, as well as the potential gain in increasing understanding and tackling biological invasions successfully globally (from very low to very high).

Process overview

Coordinating lead authors have identified the most important knowledge gaps in their chapter and invited the rest of the group (lead authors, fellows) to assess the estimated costs, scientific challenge to close these gaps, as well as the potential gain in increasing understanding and tackling biological invasions successfully globally.

Protocol

1. Identification of knowledge gaps

Coordinating lead authors were asked to identify the most important (5 to 10) knowledge and data gaps from their own chapter. Results can be accessed at "Synthesis-knowledge gaps.xls".

2. Assessment of costs, challenges and potential gains associated with each knowledge gap

For each knowledge or data gap, experts have been invited to answer the following set of questions through Google form:

⋮

How important is it to close this gap for...

 Multiple choice grid ▼

Rows		Columns		
1. ...improving understanding of trends?	✕	<input type="radio"/> Not at all important	✕	
2. ...improving understanding of drivers?	✕	<input type="radio"/> Slightly important	✕	
3. ...improving understanding of impacts?	✕	<input type="radio"/> Important	✕	
4. ...improving management?	✕	<input type="radio"/> Fairly important	✕	
5. ...taking actions?	✕	<input type="radio"/> Very important	✕	
6. Add row		<input type="radio"/> No opinion	✕	
		<input type="radio"/> Add column		

⋮

Costs and challenges

 Multiple choice grid ▼

Description (scale, section)

Rows		Columns		
1. How costly would it be to close this gap	✕	<input type="radio"/> very low	✕	
2. How challenging (other than costs, i.e., s...	✕	<input type="radio"/> low	✕	
3. Add row		<input type="radio"/> intermediate	✕	
		<input type="radio"/> high	✕	
		<input type="radio"/> very high	✕	
		<input type="radio"/> No opinion	✕	
		<input type="radio"/> Add column		

What is the main reason this gap exists?

1. Lack of knowledge
2. Lack of availability of the knowledge

Each knowledge gap was assessed by at least 6 experts. Raw results are available at “Assessment_IAS knowledge gaps” and final results (with calculated means for each knowledge gap) are available in “Formatted”.

3. Chapter sections relevant to each knowledge gaps are added in the final table in curly brackets.